

TRANSFORMATIONS OF THE LIBRARIES INTO GREEN LIBRARIES: AN ANALYSIS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF INDIAN LIBRARIES

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The necessity of environmental preservation and energy conservation through green practices is covered in this paper. The preservation of the environment, social and economic well-being, physical and mental health, and a sustainable future for humanity are all prioritized by green practices. The library is the only option available, as it is considered a social institution that disseminates information about environmentally friendly behaviours. For this to function, the library needs to turn green. The green library uses natural building materials and biodegradable products, recycles waste materials responsibly, conserves energy, water, and paper, and carefully selects sites to minimize negative environmental impact and maximize indoor environmental quality. It also emphasizes the library's moral obligation to promote environmental sustainability. Building green libraries is essential in a country like India, where the fast population growth has a detrimental effect on the environment and natural resources.

Value: This study demonstrates that a big budget is not necessary for the establishment of a green library. To make the library green, all that is needed is knowledge of green practices and efforts, along with the assistance of capable stakeholders. LIS specialists will thus benefit from this study's planning assistance for green libraries.

Keywords: Energy Conservation, Green Building, Green Codes, Green Library, Green Practice, Green Services, IGBC, Sustainable Library.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to factors like climate change, poor global air quality, and general environmental degradation, it is becoming increasingly difficult for our lovely planet to maintain its natural beauty. These are, without a doubt, some of the most horrific problems the world is now dealing with. In addition to rising average temperatures, these terrifying problems include extreme weather, increasing sea levels, shifting wildlife populations and habitats, and other effects. The impact of humans on the environment is exacerbating all these changes. The

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quality of surface water pollution, greenhouse gas emissions, resource consumption, and climate change are typical consequences of human environmental activity. Humans can sometimes directly or indirectly cause these impacts. The utilization of technology to enhance and simplify human life is a contemporary phenomenon that warrants discussion in this context. It is a serious environmental hazard. Pollution, radiation risks, resource exploitation, etc., are the origins of the threat. All these problems seriously threaten the earth's ability to sustain its life. Global organizations are, therefore, making an attempt to become more environmentally friendly as they become aware of the harmful repercussions of their operations. The preservation of the environment, social and economic well-being, physical and mental health, and a sustainable future for humanity are all prioritized by green practices. The library is the only option available, as it is considered a social institution that disseminates information about environmentally friendly behaviours. To be done correctly, the library must first change into a green library. Green libraries are “designed to minimize the negative impact on the natural environment and maximize indoor environmental quality through careful site selection, use of natural construction materials and biodegradable products, conservation of resources (water, energy, paper), and responsible waste disposal (recycling, etc.),” according to the Online Dictionary for Library and Information Science (ODLIS). They also emphasize libraries' civic duty as pioneers in environmental sustainability. The creation of green libraries is crucial in a nation like India, where the population's rapid increase is negatively impacting the environment and natural resources.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To explore how libraries can be transformed into green libraries in India.
- To discuss standards for green libraries, highlighting the Indian Green Building Council (IGBC).
- To inform about green library initiatives in India.

3. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Bhattacharyya¹ (2017) discussed that green libraries, which stand for libraries, built with the intent to protect the environment and safeguard the community, can again prove their social responsibilities by creating awareness about green practices.

Rabidas² (2016) dealt with what green library buildings are, how they are accredited, what the things required are, and what the future of green library buildings is in modern India.

Sarswat and Kamal³ (2015) discussed the applicability of passive and low-energy cooling technologies and ventilation techniques inspired by India's past to make green libraries in the context of composite climate.

Kurbanoglu and Boustany⁴ (2014) proposed how information literacy and its instruction can be transformed into green and contribute to the green library movement.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study focuses on the seven green features- sustainable architecture and design, energy efficiency, water conservation, indoor environmental quality, building materials and resources, and innovation and development- as defined by the Indian Green Building Council (IGBC). It describes how Indian libraries might transform into green libraries. Certain traits of green buildings have been taken into consideration in order to handle the library's transformation into a green library from an Indian perspective.

The focus of this study is on how libraries in India can become green libraries by implementing the seven green features identified by the Indian Green Building Council (IGBC):

- (i) Eco-Friendly Architectural & Design,
- (ii) Site Selection and Planning,
- (iii) Water Conservation,
- (iv) Efficiency in Energy Use,
- (v) Resources and Building Materials,
- (vi) The quality of the indoor environment and
- (vii) Innovation and Development. For green libraries, specific characteristics of green buildings have been considered.

5. TRANSFORMATION OF LIBRARY INTO GREEN LIBRARY

5.1 Sustainable Architecture and Design

When preparing the library building, care should be given to protect the site features to minimize damage and the associated adverse effects on the environment. IGBC states that the following must be maintained: 50% of the site's contour, 100% of the water bodies and channels, 50% of natural rocks, 10% of the current topography and scenery, and 75% of the trees (with integration). Library buildings should also incorporate passive architectural design elements to reduce adverse environmental effects. These can be achieved by using climate-responsive concepts and design elements like skylights, shading from surrounding trees and buildings, punched windows, extended louvres, and passive cooling/heating technologies like wind towers, earth tunnels, and geothermal technologies.

5.2 Site Selection and Planning

People will use the library more frequently if certain basic amenities are located adjacent to it or at least one kilometre away. Some amenities include a grocery store, pharmacy, post office, courier service, restaurant, cafeteria, ATM/bank, clinic/hospital, and utility bill payment centre. Administrators of libraries should encourage their clients to take public transit in order to lessen the negative consequences of driving. A bus stop, an intra-city rail station, or other public transportation hubs should, therefore, be 800 meters away by

foot from the library. Library users should be encouraged to utilize non-fossil fuel vehicles, such as electric or compressed natural gas (CNG)-powered automobiles, to reduce the negative consequences of fossil fuel-powered autos. Within five kilometres of the library, CNG filling stations and electric charging stations must be set up with the assistance of the relevant authorities. In order to minimize long-term detrimental effects on the ecosystem, an effort should be made to restore the land while the library building is being prepared. For this reason, it is important to protect already-existing mature trees and to plant new tree saplings in order to enhance habitat and biodiversity. The library building will receive plenty of shade from the existing trees on its west and south faces, which will help to lower the building's temperature. High solar reflectance index (SRI) materials, such as white or light-coloured China mosaic tiles, white cement tiles, or other highly reflective materials/coatings, should be used to cover library roofs to limit the heat island effect and lessen its detrimental effects on the microclimate. Another way to lower heat is by using vegetation on the roof. Senior folks and people with disabilities should also have easy access to library buildings through design. To raise awareness among library patrons, a few fundamental rules of green building ought to be posted at the entrance, on a notice board, beside the circulation desk, and in the reading area.

5.3 Water Conservation

“Groundwater levels in various parts of the country are declining because of continuous withdrawal due to increased demand for freshwater for various uses, vagaries of rainfall, increased population, industrialization, and urbanization,” according to the Jal Shakti Ministry, Government of India. Water usage must be used correctly from the beginning. In this regard, the library needs to lead by example as well. Libraries can save water in so many different ways. Water can be saved significantly by using toilets and sinks appropriately. For that, water-efficient plumbing fixtures (as applicable) whose flow rates meet the baseline criteria in aggregate can be used. Rainwater also has to be preserved from library roof catchment, gutters, down pipes in filter chambers, storage tanks/pits/sumps, and groundwater recharge structures like pits, trenches, tube wells, or a combination of the above structures for storage of rainwater on the surface for future use and recharge to groundwater. This way, we can collect a good amount of water, which can be used for washroom, cleaning, and gardening purposes in the library. Collected rainwater can be cleaned following a simple sedimentation process, which is a process of suspending the insoluble/heavy particles from the water. Once the insoluble material settles down at the bottom, we can separate the pure water. Simple chemical treatment involves the use of chlorine, which is commonly used to kill bacteria, which decomposes water by adding contaminants to it. Another oxidizing agent used for purifying the water is ozone. This cleaned water can be used in basins along with toilets and gardening. Besides this, plantation in library surroundings area or landscape area should be done with drought tolerant or native or adaptive species like Palash or dhak (*Buteamonosperma*),

Amaltash (*Cassia fistula*), Amla (*Emblicoefficialis*) Neem (*Azadirachtaindica*), Jarul (*Lagerstroemia flos-reginae*), Siris (*Albizialebbeck*), Imli(*Tamarindusindicus*), Peepal (*Ficusreligiosa*), etc. so that they do not require supplemental irrigation or very less water is required.

5.4 Energy Efficiency

In the library, we have to try to use eco-friendly heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning (HVAC) equipment which are CFC (Chloro Fluoro Carbon) free, thereby minimizing the negative impact on the ozone layer. The fire extinguisher installed in the library should be free from Halons or any other ozone-depleting substances. The lights, air-conditioning systems, heating system, fans, pump and motors and other electrical gadgets used in the library should be of a standard which consumes less energy. The library should also install solar panels on the library rooftop to produce electricity. Libraries belonging to hill areas can install wind turbines to produce electricity. Both renewable sources are clean and cost-effective. Another source of renewable energy, i.e., biomass, can be installed in rural libraries to produce energy. It is also clean and carbon-free. All these renewable sources of energy help to minimize the environmental impacts associated with the use of fossil fuel energy. A library can feel less institutional and more personal by making good use of daylight, which can also save energy consumption. Uncontrolled daylighting, however, has the potential to cause glare and harm delicate materials. Windows or clerestories that face northward let in light but block out direct sunshine. Adequate overhangs and south-facing glazing can also work well. Adjustable window coverings should be available when natural sunlight is permitted in reading spaces. As a result, using as much daylight as possible to improve the library's visibility lowers expenses and energy consumption.

5.5 Building Materials and Resources

5.5.1 Sustainable Building Materials

The Indian central government founded the Building Materials and Technology Promotion Council (BMTPC) in 1990 to advance building materials and technologies that are reasonably priced, ecologically benign, and energy efficient. Among the natural elements that BMTPC deemed potentially acceptable building materials were agro-industrial wastes, by-products, residues, natural fibres, and plantation timbers, such as rice and wheat husk, bagasse from sugarcane, coir, hemp, etc., that are cultivated extensively in Indian farms. Because of their durability, accessibility, and affordability, a few of these state-of-the-art green building materials stand out in particular. These include bamboo as a building material, bagasse particle board, and concrete made of rice husk ash. When developing a new library structure in India, these eco-friendly building elements must be taken into account.

5.5.2 Green Library Furniture

For library furniture, a large range of environmentally friendly furnishing materials are available. The robustness, durability, and elegance of the ecological library furniture are guaranteed. The following well-liked environmentally friendly building materials can be utilized to create library furniture: Six Bamboo furniture is as strong as furniture made of any other wood. Bamboo is useful for building ladders, bookcases in the library, tables, seats, and sofa sets. There are many different sources of reclaimed wood, such as lumber that washes up from rivers, imperfect wood, and insect-infested trees that had to be chopped down. Reclaimed wood enhances the library's visual appeal while contributing to its feeling of a deep, mysterious past, thanks to the antique treatment. Now, lantana wood closely resembles cane and bamboo in quality, so it's a less expensive option. Lantana is a non-edible decorative weed plant that was introduced to India and has now become an invasive species, strangling native plants throughout forests. Its tough stem can withstand termites and, with varnish treatment, maintain its glossy, smooth appearance. Bookcases, trays for library cards, couches, and chairs could all be made with it.

5.5.3 Green Collections and Collection Development

Three approaches can be used to discuss green collections and collection development: choosing materials that promote environmentally friendly behaviours, de-selection procedures that emphasize the value and technique of material reuse and recycling and choosing information sources (print or electronic) that emit fewer greenhouse gases. Selection: Its main objective is to gather data from sources that address environmental issues, pollution prevention, water and energy conservation, etc. Books, journals, reference tools, and e-resources are some of the information sources. The proliferation of information literacy on the green movement is aided by all those information sources. De-selection: This method stresses reusing books, journals, and periodicals that have been weeded out in good physical condition. It can be distributed to poor neo-literates and semi-literates in rural or slum areas instead of just throwing away. The damaged paper-based materials should be recycled to enhance the green practice. However, recycling e-waste is really a problematic issue. Format of Information Sources: It indicates the two formats, i.e., print and electronic, of information sources found in the library. Which one is a more suitable format for the green library is to be looked into. Print and electronic media both have positive and negative impacts on the environment. Both can be sustainable, but both will need to become far more eco-efficient over the next years.

5.5.4 Green Services

Quality service makes a library effective to its users and attracts the user community to be involved with the library. The green library movement is influencing libraries to offer services in an eco-friendly mode. They are:

- The library should provide clean printed information sources that are not hazardous to the health of its users.

- At the time of providing information for stereotyped reference queries, the librarian should not unnecessarily use the internet; rather, s/he would use his/her own memory to provide prompt service.
- In addition to the green environment in the library, the services are tried to offer less energy. Users are motivated to use computers and the internet judiciously. Unnecessary printouts and photocopies should be avoided. They should be done using both sides of the paper. The font size of the printout matter should not exceed 12. In this regard, it is to be mentioned here that a growing number of companies like Apple, Facebook, and Google have begun to produce green internet and browsers based on renewable energy. Green Library has to incorporate all those green internet and browsers to enhance the green practice.
- To help staff and users have a clear understanding of green practices and to encourage them to adopt green practices in order to assist others in greening their own lives, facilities, and operations, libraries should organize orientation programs, seminars, conferences, library talks, and workshops on green practices in addition to disseminating information about these practices through a variety of information sources.

5.5.5 Waste Management

In the library, three types of solid waste or garbage are generated. They are organic waste, toxic waste, and recyclable waste. Organic waste includes residual parts of foods, vegetables, flowers, leaves, and fruits. Toxic waste covers old medicines, paints, chemicals, bulbs, spray cans, pesticide containers, batteries, and e-waste, including computers, UPS, printers, scanners, photocopiers, etc. Recyclable waste includes paper, glass, metals, and plastics. These three types of waste should be kept in separate baskets in the library. For that, instructions should be given very clearly at the place where the baskets would be placed. The instructions should also be written on the baskets so that library staff and users can easily understand the type of waste and its disposal in the right basket. The baskets of organic and toxic waste, excluding e-waste, should be handed over to the garbage-carrying car of the municipality/corporation. The e-waste has to be managed following the rules of E-Waste (Management) Amendment Rules, 2018, in India. The recyclable waste has to be handed over to the proper agencies that deal with all kinds and grades of recyclable waste and facilitate recycling and reuse. Landfill facilities, at least for organic waste, can be arranged in library premises in rural areas, which can be recycled by the method of composting, one of the oldest forms of disposal. It is the natural process of decomposition of organic waste that yields manure or compost, which is very rich in nutrients.

5.6 Indoor Environmental Quality

The quality of the air we breathe indoors is crucial to our health. Unfortunately, materials that may be harmful to our health can be found in modern libraries. These can be anything from harmless dust to dangerous substances. Indoor air in libraries is essentially tainted by chemical and biological pollutants. Dust mites, pollen, animal dander, bacteria, and

molds are the biological pollutants. In the printed materials of the library, Molds emit both fumes and spores. Employees and patrons at libraries may inhale mould spores, which can lead to infections, irritation of the skin and eyes, and respiratory issues. Particulates and gases are among the chemical pollutants. One of the main chemical contaminants in the library is formaldehyde, which can be harmful to health and may be a carcinogen. It enters the building through an adhesive called urea-formaldehyde, which is found in pressed wood products, including particleboard, cabinetry, and trim. Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) are also harmful to health and can be found in libraries, particularly in particleboard, wood panelling, carpets, paints, glues, varnishes, and solvents. An imbalance in the proper balance of gases and the production of carbon dioxide within the library is caused by the HVAC system's existence and improper/regular maintenance. Lack of maintenance on the HVAC system also negatively affects humidity regulation, creating an ideal environment for the growth of bacteria, mould, and mildew. The routine pest control with strong chemicals like toxic organo-phosphate and carbamate insecticides in the library also contaminates the indoor air quality of the library.

The environment of the library can be healthy by following some simple and careful steps. First of all, regular cleaning of the library floor, furniture, and resources should be done to make it dust and moisture-free, along with the provision of adequate sunlight. The green movement has prompted the development of long-lasting, reasonably priced, and less hazardous paints and finishes with low or zero volatile organic compounds (VOCs) for the environment and human health. The library should employ these common- and zero-VOC paints and finishes. Our native cooling and ventilation method, which was widely used in the palaces of Rajasthan, Gujarat, and the Mughals, can replace the HVAC systems in the library. The orientation of the structure, thermal mass, water feature, open courtyard, several types of shading devices, flora, lattice screens, domes, charkhas, wind towers, air vents, and other magnificent design elements were all employed in those palaces to provide thermal comfort.

5.7 Innovation and Development

The library needs to incorporate more cutting-edge features that aren't adequately outlined in green building standards, such as energy efficiency, waste management, novel structural design, and library services. This will improve the library's sustainability initiatives. Green Building Council-accredited professionals must be involved to make the library green. Additionally, a "green budget" should be created for the library. The green budget is one area where promoting constructive behaviour and discouraging environmental harm affects how humans interact with the environment.

6. GREEN CODES

To promote the design, development, construction, and maintenance of green buildings, the US Green Building Council established the LEED rating system in 1993.

To further the nation's green building movement, the Indian Green Building Code collaborates closely with several Central and State Government agencies. It is an amalgam of the Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC), the National Building Code, State bylaws, the Indian Green Building Council (IGBC) standards and guidelines for the residential sector, TERI-GRIHA, and other comparable certifications, the protocols developed by rating programs such as Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design India (LEED-India), and other sources. A few Central and State Government entities have acknowledged the IGBCs' Green Rating Systems.

7. GREEN LIBRARY INITIATIVES IN INDIA

Anna Centenary Library (ACL), Chennai: It is a state-of-the-art library that was opened to the public on 20 September 2010. The positive aspect of ACL indicates that in terms of occupant comfort, the library performs well in its design. The library has achieved a gold rating from LEED.

Karnataka University Library, Dharwad: Karnataka University has incorporated the Gurukul system to provide library services. The university has arranged the reading space in a natural green environment with sitting, drinking, and WiFi facilities.

NIT Library, Silchar: The Library of NIT, Silchar, is the first green initiative in northeast India. It was built following the LEED, USA, green certification system. It is really a role model for green library initiatives in India.

PermaKarlo Library, Ladakh: It is truly an amazing piece of work and the ideal illustration of how science, smart design, and local expertise came together to produce a library building that is both beautiful and sustainable. On-site, technological and design choices include timber panelling, wool insulation, vented Trombe walls, mud roofs, and even solar panels mounted on the roof. To guarantee that the knowledge is retained, the materials are sourced locally, and the design solutions and experience are developed in collaboration with the individuals present.

8. FINDINGS

It has been mentioned that creating green libraries requires meticulous design in accordance with green building standards. Buildings used by libraries must be equipped with features for waste management, energy and water saving, and good indoor air quality. In contrast, there are three ways that collections and collection development in green libraries have been discussed: selecting print or electronic information sources that use less energy and produce less carbon dioxide; de-selection procedures that emphasize the necessity and means of material reuse and recycling; and selecting materials that support the spread of awareness about green practices. Conversely, research indicates that green services consume less paper and energy. Furthermore, studies have shown that the transformation of Indian libraries

into “green” libraries will be financially advantageous due to the application of specific local techniques for ensuring the sustainability of libraries. The use of easily obtained agricultural products for construction and furnishings, natural pesticides, recycling techniques, and other notable ventilation and cooling techniques used in Indian palaces are all worthy of attention. The IGBC and Indian green library projects have also been discussed, along with a few other green codes.

9. CONCLUSION

In India, regarding her present condition in terms of the environment and conservation of natural resources, green practices have become very crucial for sustainability. The library, which is considered a social institution, has to take the leading role in spreading awareness about green practices. For that, libraries have to be transformed into green libraries. This transformation should be enhanced with the help of central and state governments, NGOs, library associations, and, obviously, Library and Information Science professionals.

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